

Statement of Contribution

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The work presented in this thesis is the work that I Rhaunav Kumar, completed between 04/08/2023 and 14/11/2023 under the supervision of Dr Elizabeth Stratton.

Formulation of ideas/hypothesis

Formulation of ideas and hypotheses were completed by Rhaunav Kumar under the supervision of Dr Elizabeth Stratton.

Data Collection

Data was collected prior to the beginning of the project and data handling was securely stored on University of Sydney Databases with permission granted to student for use in a secondary analysis project.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

The statistical techniques used in this report were guided by Dr Elizabeth Stratton. Data analysis and interpretation were conducted by Rhaunav Kumar with assistance by the supervisor in the Professor Marie Bashir Building and University of Sydney Brain and Mind Centre.

Writing

Work written and compiled by Rhaunav Kumar and critique and suggestions were provided by the supervisor.

The remainder of the thesis contains work that is my own in its entirety. Any referral to previously published work is clearly indicated throughout the text.

Validating Subjective Mental Health Assessment Tools in a Male Dominated Workplace

Abstract

Introduction

This research explores the escalating prevalence of mental health disorders, specifically depression and anxiety, in the Australian mining industry, emphasizing the under-addressed challenges faced by male workers. The study aims to assess the accuracy of self-report measures through psychometric analysis, seeking to improve mental health interventions in this hard-to-reach population.

Methodology

In this cross-sectional study of 136 Australian miners, participants were recruited online, with confidentiality ensured through authorized staff access. Inclusion criteria involved internet access and English proficiency, excluding those receiving interventions. A comprehensive survey assessed demographics, employment, and mental health using self-report (PHQ-9, GAD-7) and clinician-administered (MINI) measures. Statistical analyses, including correlation matrices, aimed to evaluate psychometric properties and establish relationships between subjective and objective assessments.

Results

The mean PHQ-9 score was 4.57 (SD=3.78). Twelve participants met the depression cut-off (66% male). Overall, 58% had nil to minimal depression, 4.4% met the clinician-rated MINI MDD criteria. The mean GAD-7 score was 4.26 (SD = 3.76). Thirty-seven percent met the criteria for mild anxiety and 8.8% met the GAD-7 cut-off for generalised anxiety disorder and six (4.4%) met the clinician rated MINI GAD criteria. The PHQ-9 demonstrated a Cronbach's alpha of 0.851 and the GAD-7 demonstrated a Cronbach's alpha of 0.875. The PHQ-9 demonstrated a Positive Predictive Value of 41% and a Negative Predictive Value of 99%. The GAD-7 exhibited a Positive Predictive Value of 26% and a Negative Predictive Value of 98%.

Conclusion

The tools show good internal consistency. However, low positive predictive values suggest caution. Future research should address sample size, biases, and time differences in symptom measurement, ensuring robustness before implementing in mental health applications.

Introduction

Background and Rationale

The National Study of Mental Health and Wellbeing in 2021 estimated 8.6 million Australians between ages 16 and 85 experienced a mental disorder in their lifetime (Australia Bureau of Statistics [ABS], 2022). Between 2014/2015 to 2017/2018 there has been an increase in the prevalence of mental or behavioural conditions from 18% to 20%. This was largely due to increase in diagnoses of anxiety and depression (ABS, 2017-2018).

The burden of disease of depression greatly contributes to the global economic burden of mental illness (Roche et al., 2016). Specifically, The Global Burden of Disease Study highlights worldwide depression has increased from 172 million cases in 1990 to 258 million cases in 2017 (Liu et al., 2020).

Depression can be characterised by periods of sadness, low mood, irritability and a loss of interest and pleasure (Rondón Bernard, 2018). Major depressive disorder is a result of prolonged depression as the DSM-V criteria highlights depressive symptoms such as depressed mood and anhedonia must be present for most of the day, every day for two weeks (American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2022). Often co-diagnosed with MDD, Generalised Anxiety Disorder is characterised by persistent and excessive concerns related to interpersonal relationships, health and over analysing social situations (APA, 2022). Complications of GAD may include, disturbed sleep and irritability which have been shown to hinder work ability, places strain on education and health care services (Allgulander, 2012).

Men's mental health has been an area of focus as men tend to be less help-seeking, have lower mental health literacy, experience more stigmatisation due to masculinity norms, and are impacted by gender norms more broadly (McKenzie et al., 2022), (Sagar-Ouriaghli et al.,

2019). There are notable gender differences between male and female mental health. Males are more likely to report having a lifetime mental health disorder (48.1%) compared to females (43%) (ABS, 2020-2022). The Australian Longitudinal Male study of health reports that up to 25% of men have been diagnosed with a mental health disorder in their lifetime (Australian Institute of Family Studies, 2022). Depression is the most prevalent mental health disorder for men at 13% compared to 11.6% in 2017-2018 for women (ABS, 2017-2018). Between 2020-2021 12.4% of males had a 12-month long anxiety disorder with females 1.5 times more likely to have an anxiety related disorder (ABS, 2017-2018). Men account for over 75% of deaths by suicide in Australia (Australian Institute of Health and Welfare, 2023) and this trend is mirrored on a global scale, as males constitute the majority of suicides (Ilic & Ilic, 2022).

Major depressive disorder in the workplace has been shown by the National Comorbidity Survey Replication in the United States, to negatively impact on workplace attendance and work performance (Kessler et al., 2006). Specifically 8.7 work days are lost per person due to absenteeism as a result of MDD and 18.2 work days are lost due to reduced work performance as a result of MDD (Kessler et al., 2006). Generalised anxiety disorder in the workplace has been shown to reduce work accomplishment in an Australian survey of 37580 working age individuals (Waghorn & Chant, 2006). Anxiety was also a factor for work restrictions which compounded the reduction in work accomplishment (Waghorn & Chant, 2006).

Male dominated industries are defined as >70% male employees and includes the mining industry (Roche et al., 2016). Common workplace factors such as poor lifestyle choices, overworking and stressful work environment contribute to anxiety and depression (Battams et al., 2014). The seasonal and remote nature of the mining industry, including fly-in-fly-out work leads to extended periods of social isolation, making access to mental health interventions challenging, which contributes to mental ill health (Brook et al., 2020). A qualitative study exploring men's use of mental health services suggests men avoid help seeking due to workplace culture, scepticism, and a belief that help is not needed (Matthews et al., 2021). These reasons are compounded by stigma and traditional masculine norms enforcing men to emotionally restrict themselves (Matthews et al., 2021). This leads to an underutilisation of mental health services and possibly underdiagnoses of mental health conditions (Matthews et al., 2021). Mental health effects in the mining industry have been previously shown to involve high levels of psychological distress in the form of financial

stress, interpersonal relationships, work stress and social isolation (Bowers et al., 2018). Subsequently, there is an imperative to address symptoms before employees are too unwell.

Gaps in Literature and Research Question

To explore the prevalence of mental health conditions in the workplace in a sector that is hard to reach due to the precarious nature of fly-in-fly-out it is important to consider novel approaches to assessing mental ill health in hard to reach populations. One way to manage this is by delivering self-report measures online. However, it is unknown if these self-report measures are accurate. Are people with mental health symptoms able to identify their symptoms and report them correctly?

Current recommendations highlight subjective assessment is varied (Newson et al., 2020). Some empirical research suggests it may be unsuitable for lone diagnosis (Mulrow, 1995); other literature demonstrates self-reports are an accurate diagnostic assessment for health disorders (Newson et al., 2020). Eliminating the need for clinician assessments, in these hard to reach workplace setting may increase men's willingness to access mental health interventions.

Psychometric Evidence

To assess the effectiveness of self-reporting in identifying mental ill-health a technique known as psychometric analysis will be employed. Psychometric analyses elucidate the reliability and validity of instruments, in this instance add evidence to the accuracy and reproducibility of self-report assessments in this setting (Souza et al., 2017).

This study utilised a cross-sectional observation into a sample of Australian Miners recruited from Western Australia via online survey. Self-administered subjective assessment instruments (Patient Health Questionnaire - 9 [PHQ-9] and Generalised Anxiety Disorder 7 – item scale [GAD-7]) were used to gather data regarding MDD and GAD. The MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview for Major Depressive Disorder and Generalised Anxiety Disorder represented the objective assessment instruments researchers and clinicians used to collect mental health information. The MINI has been shown to be a valid and

reliable assessment for neuropsychiatric diagnosis, making it an accurate comparator for subjective assessments (Pettersson et al., 2018).

Aims

In the current study we sought to evaluate the psychometric properties of the PHQ-9 and GAD-7 in diagnosing MDD and GAD. This includes analysing the internal consistency, sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value and overall accuracy of the instruments compared to clinician rated scales. Our study aims to achieve this by generating correlation matrices.

Hypotheses

It is hypothesised that the internal consistency reliability of the both PHQ-9 and GAD-7 will show acceptable values and correlation matrices will demonstrate acceptable positive predictive values and negative predictive values in identifying MDD and GAD, respectively compared to clinician rated scales.

Methods

Participants

Recruitment

The current study recruited participants from an Australian mining company, situated throughout Western Australia, via online survey. The data set is from a sample of 136 employees.

Participants were recruited via company email invitations and promotional information on company workplace sites and websites. Consent was obtained via a written consent form and having data exclusive to authorised staff ensured confidentiality. Ethics approval was authorised by The University of Sydney Ethics Committee.

Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria

The study included participants with access to the internet, and those fluent in the English language. The study excluded participants receiving interventions following baseline assessments.

Study Design

A cross-sectional design was employed for the evaluation of participants' responses between subjective and objective assessment tools of depression and anxiety at a specific point in time.

Assessment

Data collection occurred between July and August 2016. The secure and confidential storage of participant data has been maintained on password-protected files at University of Sydney sites. Participants were invited to complete an online survey with the ability to navigate back and forth in a single session.

Demographics

The survey involved questions regarding demographic details of the participants. Participants reported information on:

Personal: Age (<24, 25-34, 35-44, 45-54, 55+), gender assigned at birth (Male/Female), marital status (never married, married/de facto, not married), identity as Aboriginal or Torres Strait Islander, financially dependent upon them (yes/no), number financially dependent (none, 1-2, 3+),

Employment and education: fly-in-fly-out status, education level (Primary, secondary, diploma or certificate, trade certificate, University Bachelor's, University postgraduate).

Outcome Measures:

1. Depression

Subjective

To investigate the subjective measures of depression the study utilized the PHQ-9 via self-report. Participants accessed a website link to the self-administered questionnaire. The PHQ-9 measures depression severity in participants within the last two weeks, over 9 questions and employs a Likert rating system ranging from 0-3 to represent the frequency of depressive symptoms experienced (not at all, several days, more than half the days, nearly every day). The questions aim to represent diagnostic criteria for major depression as listed in the DSM-V (APA, 2022). They explore: (1) Interest or pleasure in doing things, (2) feeling down, depressed or hopeless, (3) trouble falling or staying asleep and excessive sleeping, (4) feeling tired, (5) poor appetite or overeating, (6) feeling bad about yourself e.g. you are a failure, (7) trouble concentrating e.g. reading or watching television, (8) Noticeably moving or speaking slowly or being restless, and (9) thoughts you would be better off dead or self-harming thoughts. Scores are categorised whereby 1-4 represents minimal depression, 5-9 mild depression, 10-14 moderate depression, and 15-19 moderately severe depression and 20-27 severe depression.

Objective

The primary objective measure of depression by a clinician was the MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview for Major Depressive Disorder (version 7.0), conducted by a trained clinician. The MINI consists of six items aimed at addressing criteria for MDD as set out in the DSM-V. This is a clinician directed diagnostic assessment tool, whereby a clinician will sequentially ask yes or no questions until the end of the assessment whereby a cutoff amount of five ‘Yes’ answers qualifies for an MDD diagnosis.

2. Anxiety

Subjective

To investigate the subjective measures of anxiety the study utilized the Generalised Anxiety Disorder 7 by self-report. Participants accessed a website link to the self-administered assessment. This is a 7-item scale using a Likert rating system ranging from 0-3 to represent the frequency of anxiety symptoms experienced within the last two weeks (not at all, several days, more than half the days, nearly every day). The questions aim to represent diagnostic criteria for generalized anxiety disorder as listed in the DSM-V (APA, 2022). They explore: (1) feeling nervous or on edge, (2) not being able to stop or control worrying, (3) worrying too much about different things, (4) trouble relaxing, (5) being so restless that it is hard to sit still, (6) becoming easily annoyed or irritable, and (7) feeling afraid as if something awful might happen. Scores are categorised whereby 0-4 represents minimal anxiety, 5-9 mild anxiety, 10-14 moderate anxiety and 15-21 severe anxiety.

Objective

The objective measure of generalized anxiety disorder was the MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview – Generalised Anxiety Disorder (version 7.0) administered by a trained clinician in person. The MINI consists of seven items aimed at addressing criteria for GAD as set out in the DSM-V. As with the MINI MDD, the clinician sequentially ask yes or no questioning until the end of the assessment whereby a yes or no outcome for GAD is determined.

Statistical Analysis

All data were analysed with Jamovi version 2.4.1.0. Demographic data were generated with respect to gender, age and indigenous status. Employment factors were coded as binary (yes/no) to demonstrate the presence of FIFO. PHQ-9, GAD-7, MINI MDD and MINI GAD scores were generated using descriptive statistics tables highlighting the frequencies, mean and standard deviation. Education status was split into levels of education such as secondary school, trade certificate, diploma, undergraduate university and postgraduate qualifications and frequencies were generated in a descriptive table. Cronbach's alpha was generated for the PHQ-9 and GAD-7 to determine internal consistency reliability. The positive predictive value and negative predictive value of the PHQ-9 and GAD-7 were determined from correlation matrices generated by Jamovi and using formula to determine the PPV and NPV. Statistical software (Jamovi) produced a correlation matrix from where the positive predictive value was calculated using the following formula: $TP/TP+FP$. The negative predictive value was calculated using the following formula: $TN/TN+FN$.

Results

A total of 136 participants were recruited for the current study and 107 were male (78.7%) and 29 were female (21.3%). The study consisted of individuals between ages 22 to 68 years and the mean age was 39.3 years. The mean age for males was 38.9 years and 40.8 years for females (Table 1). Four participants (2.9%) identified as Aboriginal or Torres Strait Islander.

Table 1. Participant demographic by age, gender and indigenous status

	Overall	Males	Females
Age	Mean = 39.2 (9.44 SD)	Mean = 38.9 (8.82 SD)	Mean = 40.8 (11.6 SD)
Gender	N = 136 (100%)	N = 107 (78.7%)	N = 29 (21.3%)
Aboriginal or Torres Strait Islander	N = 4 (2.9%)	N = 3 (2.2%)	N = 1 (0.7%)

Nine participants reported having secondary school education. Forty-three participants reported having a trade or technician certificate or an apprenticeship. Thirty-one participants reported having a certificate or diploma. Thirty-two participants reported having a university or college Bachelor's degree. Twenty-one participants reported having a university of college postgraduate degree.

Table 2. Participant demographic by educational background

Education	Frequency
FIFO	73 (53.7%)
Secondary school	9 (6.6%)
Trade or technician certificate or apprenticeship	43 (31.6%)
Other certificate or diploma	31 (22.8%)
University or college Bachelor Degree	32 (23.5%)
University or college Postgraduate Degree	21 (15.4%)

The mean PHQ-9 scores was 4.57 (SD = 3.78), males scored 4.31 (SD = 3.54) on average and females 5.55 (SD = 4.50). Twelve participants met the PHQ-9 cut-off for depression (which was determined by a ROC-Curve analysis previously performed in this sample) of this eight (66%) were male and 4 (33%) were female. According to the PHQ-9 scoring criteria, Seventy-Nine (58%) participants met the PHQ-9 criteria for nil to minimal depression with 64 (47%) of those male and 15 (11%) female. Thirty-five (25%) participants score in the range of mild depression, with 27 (19%) of those male and 8 (5%) female. Ten (7.3%) score in the range for moderate depression with 7 (5.1%) of those male and 3 (2.2%) female. Two (1.4%) participants score within a range of moderate to severe depression and both were female. One male participant met the PHQ-9 criteria for severe depression. Six (4.4%) participants met the clinician rated MINI MDD criteria for depression with 5 (3.7%) of those male and 1 (0.7%) female (Table 1).

The mean GAD7 scores was 4.26 (SD = 3.76), for males it was 3.91 (SD = 3.39) and 5.55 (SD = 4.76) for females. Fifty-one (37%) participants met the GAD-7 criteria for mild

anxiety, 34 (25%) were male and 17 (12%) were female. Twelve (8.8%) participants met the GAD-7 criteria for moderate anxiety, 7 (5.1%) were male and 5 (3.6%) were female. Three (2.2%) participants met the GAD-7 criteria for severe anxiety, 1 male and 2 were female. Twelve (8.8%) participants met the GAD-7 cut off for generalised anxiety disorder, 7 (5.1%) were male and 5 (3.6%) were female. Six participants met the MINI GAD criteria rated by a clinician for generalised anxiety disorder, all being male (Table 3).

Table 3. Prevalence of depression and anxiety categorised by PHQ-9, GAD-7, MINI MDD and MINI GAD categories.

Assessment Tool	Overall	Males	Females
PHQ9 Scores	Mean = 4.57 (3.78 SD)	Mean = 4.31 (3.54 SD)	Mean = 5.55 (4.50 SD)
PHQ9 cut-off	N = 12 (8.8%)	N = 8 (5.9%)	N = 4 (2.9%)
PHQ9 Minimal	N = 79 (58.1%)	N = 64 (47.1%)	N = 15 (11%)
PHQ9 Mild	N = 35 (25.7%)	N = 27 (19.9%)	N = 8 (5.9%)
PHQ9 Moderate	N = 10 (7.4%)	N = 7 (5.1%)	N = 3 (2.2%)
PHQ9 Moderate-Severe	N = 2 (1.5%)	N = 0 (0.0%)	N = 2 (1.5%)
PHQ9 Severe	N = 1 (0.7%)	N = 1 (0.7%)	N = 0 (0.0%)
MINI MDD	N = 6 (4.4%)	N = 5 (3.7%)	N = 1 (0.7%)
Anxiety GAD7	Mean = 4.26 (3.76 SD)	Mean = 3.91 (3.39 SD)	Mean = 5.55 (4.76 SD)
GAD7 Mild	51 (37.5%)	34 (25%)	17 (12.5%)
GAD7 Moderate	12 (8.8%)	7 (5.1%)	5 (3.7%)
GAD7 Severe	3 (2.2%)	1 (0.7%)	2 (1.5%)
GAD7 cut-off	12 (8.8%)	7 (5.1%)	5 (3.7%)
MINI GAD	6 (4.4%)	6 (4.4%)	0 (0.0%)

In this sample, the PHQ-9 demonstrates appropriate levels of internal consistency reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.851. The GAD-7 demonstrates appropriate levels of internal consistency reliability with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.875.

The Positive Predictive Value of the PHQ-9 was 41% and the Negative Predictive Value of the PHQ-9 was 99%. Twelve participants met the PHQ-9 criteria for depression and of those twelve; five participants met the objective MINI MDD criteria for depression. Seven participants met the PHQ-9 criteria for depression but did not meet the MINI MDD criteria. One participant met the cut off criteria for MINI MDD and did not meet the PHQ-9 cut off. One hundred and twenty three participants did not meet the criteria for objective or subjective depression (table 4).

Table 4. Correlation Matrix highlighting the number of True Positives, False Positive, False Negative and True Negative cases when comparing the PHQ-9 against the MINI MDD.

		Predicted Condition PHQ-9	
		Positive (PP) 12	Negative (PN) 124
Total Population	136		
Positive (P)	6	TP 5	FN 1
Negative (N)	130	FP 7	TN 123
Actual Condition			
MINI MDD			

The Positive Predictive Value of the GAD-7 was 26% and the Negative Predictive Value of the GAD-7 was 98%. Twelve participants met the GAD-7 criteria for GAD and of those twelve, two participants met the objective MINI GAD criteria for GAD. Ten participants met the GAD-7 criteria for GAD but did not meet the MINI GAD criteria. Four participants met the cut off criteria for MINI GAD and did not meet the GAD-7 cut off. One hundred and twenty participants did not meet the criteria for objective or subjective GAD (Table 5).

Table 5. Correlation Matrix highlighting the number of True Positives, False Positive, False Negative and True Negative cases when comparing the GAD-7 against the MINI GAD.

Predicted Condition GAD-7		
Total Population 136	Positive (PP) 15	Negative (PN) 121
Positive (P) 6	TP 4	FN 2
Negative (N) 130	FP 11	TN 119
Actual Condition MINI GAD		

Discussion

This cross-sectional study of 136 employees evaluated the specificity and sensitivity of the PHQ-9 and GAD-7 in a male dominated sample in comparison to clinician rated assessment tools of anxiety and depression including, the MINI MDD and MINI GAD. This study uses a novel approach to assess the psychometric properties of subjective mental health assessment tools against objective mental health assessment tools in a male dominated Australian mining sample.

This sample reported overall good mental health. On average mild levels of depression were observed. Similarly, in this sample only minimal levels of anxiety were observed. This is consistent with our objective findings as a low (4.4%) proportion of individuals met the clinician cut off for GAD and MDD in the MINI. Given that our sample consists of a male majority, a possible explanation for the low subjective and objective scores is the response bias hypothesis, which reflects men's tendency to underreport symptoms of depression (Sigmon et al., 2005). Research highlights gender norms and personal views towards mental health can contribute to underreporting (Sigmon et al., 2005). Previous studies also found that men are more likely to underreport depressive symptoms when they are made aware a potential follow up will occur, as with our current study (Sigmon et al., 2005).

Can we rely on self-report measures?

Depression

The positive predictive value of the PHQ-9 was 41%, highlighting that self-report measures in our sample did not accurately predict depression diagnosed by objective measures. Issues that can arise from a low PPV include individuals without depression being identified as having depression (Shin et al., 2019). This is not unlike previous self-rated tools whereby the Zung Self-Rating Depression Scale compared against Beck's Depression Inventory had a sensitivity ranging from 31% to 51% (Mulrow, 1995). An explanation for the low PPV in our sample is that the MINI MDD categorised only 6 individuals with depression; therefore, the low disease prevalence (4.4%) is a contributing factor for the low positive predictive value of the PHQ-9. Another possible reason for the low PPV is that this was the first study to utilise a PHQ-9 cut-point (determined by ROC curve analysis) from a previous study using the same participants (Stratton et al., 2023). Despite the number of false positives, the PHQ-9 was able

to correctly identify 5 out of 6 individuals positive for depression with only 1 false negative. A low false negative rate creates confidence around screening measures (Petticrew et al., 2001) ensuring the PHQ-9 can be effectively delivered via mental health applications to male dominated workplaces whilst avoiding type II errors.

The negative predictive value of the PHQ-9 against the MINI MDD was 99% demonstrating the discriminatory power of the PHQ-9 for highlighting the absence of depression. A previous study compared the PPV and NPV of the PHQ9 against the MINI MDD and similarly reported a PPV of 53.4% and NPV of 85.7% (Shin et al., 2019). This demonstrates a consistently high NPV, which has implications for self-administering the PHQ-9 via mental health applications, and ensuring individuals without depression are correctly identified as such. Subsequently, more studies need to highlight an acceptable PPV of self-rated tools in similar samples before we can rely on self-report measures.

Anxiety

The positive predictive value of the GAD-7 against the MINI GAD was low at 26%, highlighting that self-report measures in our sample did not accurately predict GAD diagnosed by objective measures. This leads to a greater amount of false positives in the sample, however, the GAD-7 was able to correctly identify 4 out of 6 individuals positive for anxiety with only 2 false negatives. This ensures individuals positive for the condition will be identified by the GAD-7 with low a false negative rate of 33%. Possible reasons for the low PPV in our study include the ability of the GAD-7 in miscategorising other forms of anxiety such as social anxiety disorder, as generalised anxiety disorder (Plummer et al., 2016). Literature highlights this failure in sensitivity has previously been shown in a psychiatric population (Beard & Björgvinsson, 2014).

Previous studies measuring the psychometric properties of the GAD-7 highlight that PPV and NPV have an inverse relationship regardless of the cut-off point (Ahn et al., 2019), (Byrd-Bredbenner et al., 2020). This is reflected in our study, as the NPV was high at 98%. A high NPV demonstrates participants without anxiety in male dominated industries will likely be correctly identified as true negative (Byrd-Bredbenner et al., 2020). Our study was able to demonstrate a high NPV of self-report measures, however, a high PPV is also required to confidently rely on self-report measures. Subsequently, further evidence is needed, showing an acceptable PPV of self-report measures of anxiety in similar populations. Therefore, given

the low PPV of self-report tools in our sample, it is recommended to utilise subjective assessment tools as an adjunct with objective assessment tools until further studies can validate the PPV of the PHQ-9 and GAD-7.

Limitations

This study is not without limitations. First, the sample size of the study was too small compared to larger cohorts. This may have understated the true cases of depression and anxiety resulting in lower sensitivity and specificity compared to previous studies. Second, the GAD-7 assesses symptoms within the last two weeks whereas the MINI GAD assesses symptoms for the previous 6 months. This is a large difference in time, which could explain the low PPVs in our study. Third, the PHQ-9 assesses depressive symptoms within the last two weeks whereas the MINI MDD assesses symptoms for the previous 6 months, thus explaining the low PPVs in our study. Fourth, this study required the validation of self-reported measures. This can introduce biases such as recall bias regarding symptoms, however, the brevity of the PHQ-9 and GAD-7 can avoid this. Conversely, our study illuminates the importance of self-report measures highlighting they have diagnostic utility within an overlooked population. This is supported by previous studies that show individuals' feelings and perception towards their own mental health captures an insight not available in objective testing (Glozier et al., 2010). Moreover, gender bias such as toughness and anti-femineity can dissuade participants from accurately completing questionnaires (Sileo & Kershaw, 2020). Fifth, recruitment bias may exist as the study was voluntary, therefore individuals interested in mental health assessment can conflate results.

Conclusion

This study presents psychometric properties of the Patient Health Questionnaire - 9 and the Generalised Anxiety Disorder - 7 item scale within a male dominated Australian industry. The results suggest the PHQ-9 is a reliable predictor of negative predictive value compared to the MINI Interview for Major Depressive Disorder and the GAD-7 is a reliable predictor of negative predictive value compared to the MINI Interview for Generalised Anxiety Disorder. The PHQ-9 and the GAD-7 demonstrate good internal consistency. This study further highlights the PHQ-9 and GAD-7 have low positive predictive value due to precipitating factors. These can be addressed in future studies by ensuring a larger sample size, accounting for self-report biases and the time difference in measuring symptoms between subjective and objective assessments, and avoiding gender bias by implementing screening questions regarding masculine norms during recruitment to filter out these participants. This study demonstrates acceptable reliability and validity of the PHQ-9 and GAD-7 in a male dominated sample, having implications for male industry screening, future cohort studies and national health programs. Despite promising results, further cohort studies investigating the positive predictive value of the PHQ-9 and GAD-7 are required before confidently implementing subjective tools via mental health applications in place of clinician directed assessments.

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